

Species	Busco groups searched	Busco notation assessment results
<i>Festulolium braunii</i> (LM x FP)	1440	C:70.4%[S:19.3%,D:51.1%],F:14.4%,M:15.2%
<i>Festulolium pabulare</i> (LM x FA) <i>festucoid</i>	1440	C:67.9%[S:18.3%,D:49.6%],F:19.2%,M:12.9%
<i>Festulolium pabulare</i> (LM x FA) <i>festucoid</i>	1440	C:67.9%[S:16.9%,D:51.0%],F:14.9%,M:17.2%
<i>Festulolium pabulare</i> (LM x FA) <i>loloid</i>	1440	C:68.6%[S:19.0%,D:49.6%],F:19.1%,M:12.3%